

METHODS USED IN DEVELOPING THE COGNITIVE ACTIVITY OF PRIMARY STUDENTS

Ismailova Nozimakhan

NamDU researcher

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Abstract: In this article pedagogical and didactic conditions necessary for the development of cognitive activity of primary school students, classification of stages and levels of development of cognitive activity, and It discusses methods used to develop the cognitive activity of primary school students.

Keywords: cognitive activity, free thinking, creative tasks, didactic games, Project method, problem situations

Annotation: V dannoy state rassmatrivayutsya pedagogic and didactic conditions, neobhodimye dlya razvitiya poznavatelnoy activity of young schoolchildren, classification stage and level development of poznavatelnoy activity, a takje metody, primenyaemye dlya razvitiya poznavatelnoy activity of young schoolchildren.

Key words: cognitive activity, freedom of thought, creative work, didactic games, method project, problem situation

Annotation: This article will talk about the pedagogical and didactic conditions necessary for the development of cognitive activity of primary students, the classification of stages and levels of development of cognitive activity, and the methods used in the development of cognitive activity of primary students.

Keywords: cognitive activity, free thinking, creative tasks, didactic games, Project method, problem situations

One of the most commonly used methods for developing students' cognitive activity in pedagogical activities is described as follows:

1. It is necessary to create a psychological environment in the lessons in which students feel the necessity of the learning process, accept new knowledge with interest, and eliminate situations of "boredom" at school.

The main goal of this pedagogical method is to create a psychologically comfortable and motivating environment for students in the lessons. This, in turn, increases the effectiveness of the lesson, helps students understand the content of the educational material, and prevents them from feeling overwhelmed even in the process of mastering complex academic subjects.

The following methodological recommendations are given by primary school teachers, psychologists, and methodologists for implementing the above method in school practice:

1) The following step-by-step approach is recommended when teaching students to solve problems. First, using the example of a simple problem, its solution is explained in detail step by step. Each action is divided into operations that are performed sequentially. Examples of actions and operations are given, and possible options for their implementation are shown.

As a result, a generalized scheme of methods for solving certain types of problems is formed. After that, students are presented with a similar problem and are offered to solve it independently. Using the questions presented in the text, students act in accordance with this scheme. These questions require not only the performance of operations, but also the justification of their necessity.

The next set of practice questions teaches you to perform actions in increasingly complex situations. Here, students continue to work on answering questions that are structured in a sequential manner.

The initial practice questions are appropriate for the level of compulsory education, while higher-level questions are presented in later stages. The level of complexity of these questions can be chosen independently by the student, which serves to develop in accordance with his interests and intellectual capabilities.

2) The use of video materials is one of the most effective tools in the educational process. Small videos can be used as an epigraph to the lesson, which helps to form positive emotional motivation in students towards learning a new topic.

The use of video resources in the process of explaining or reinforcing new knowledge will have a real impact only if students actively and consciously accept it. To this end, it is recommended that during the video presentation, the teacher provide comments and explanations when necessary, repeatedly show the necessary fragments, and also ask clarifying questions.

This approach ensures that students are not only visually engaged, but also cognitively engaged, encouraging them to analyze, evaluate, and connect what they see with knowledge. As a result, students are involved in the learning process not only as passive spectators, but also as active participants.

3) One of the effective methods for developing cognitive activity in students is the use of texts that are specially organized in terms of content. Such texts develop an active and reflective attitude towards knowledge in students. In particular, texts with the following characteristics are useful:

- Texts that allow students to understand that there are multiple approaches to the same situation. They teach students to look at a problem from different perspectives and encourage them to work with alternative approaches;
- texts that offer multiple solutions to a single problem, which develops students' ability to make choices and justify decision-making;
- Through texts containing contradictory information, students develop a critical approach to information, justification, and refutation-verification activities;
- the acceptance of unexpected and unusual information , which develops the ability to adapt knowledge and reason in a changing context;
- texts that contain errors and invite discussion of them, which form reflection (awareness and understanding of one's own errors) in the thinking of students;
- Texts that can provide a perspective on the material being studied in the subject, as well as allow for revisiting previously learned knowledge from a new perspective.

Such didactic materials enhance the student's participation in the learning process, turn him into a subject, and serve to form a personal position that is open, active, and ready to explore knowledge.

4) When selecting educational materials, it is necessary to take into account the different intellectual abilities of students. This approach is based on the principle of differentiated learning and ensures that students develop in accordance with their individual cognitive capabilities. In particular, special attention is paid to activating students' intuitive experience. In this process, the following are encouraged:

- to express doubt;
- expressing independent views or opinions;
- to promote "proactive" ideas on a new topic;
- Emotional evaluation of educational material.

This method activates the student's internal thought processes, connects them to their own experience, and enhances cognitive activity.

5) The formation of the ability to wonder, doubt and be surprised is an important psychological factor in the development of creative and reflective thinking of students. One of the effective ways to form these states is the use of demonstrative experiences (experiments). It is the feeling of wonder that encourages the student to independently search, to strive to find the truth. This,

in turn, increases his internal motivation to verify, substantiate and learn his assumptions.

Only a person who is able to wonder and question can become an active, independent, and creative thinker. For such a learner, knowledge becomes not only a goal, but also a means of exploration, discovery, wonder, and personal understanding.

6) Laboratory and practical classes are recommended as an important tool for developing students' creative abilities, taking into account their individual characteristics, as well as for forming independence and initiative in them. Such types of activities stimulate students' active attitude to knowledge, involve them in cognitive practical actions such as observation, analysis, testing, and drawing conclusions. Through this, students not only absorb ready-made knowledge, but also strive to find it independently.

7) Solving experimental tasks is an important methodological tool in developing creative thinking in students. The content of such tasks should be as close as possible to real-life situations. This allows students to apply the knowledge they have gained in a real context, strive to solve practical problems, and develop critical thinking skills. Through experimental tasks, students are formed not just as consumers of knowledge, but as active creators of knowledge.

2. Creative tasks. The main goal of this method is to increase students' interest in science, consolidate knowledge, and form interdisciplinary connections. Creative tasks encourage students to think unconventionally, actively involve them in the process of creating, expressing, and presenting knowledge.

Such tasks are carried out through the following non-traditional types of activities:

- create a crossword puzzle on a specific topic and use it as a tool to test other students' knowledge;
- drawing a picture depicting a topic, which provides a visual understanding of the learning material;
- creating diagrams and outlines, which forms structural thinking and develops the ability to distinguish main ideas.

At the beginning of each subsequent lesson, students' creative work is presented, discussed, and evaluated - not only by the teacher, but also by their classmates and group members. This process is important in developing skills of mutual analysis, reflection, and evaluation.

The unique feature of creative tasks is that they allow each student to express themselves, they are independent in choosing the form of activity that suits them. This approach develops the personal creative potential of students, connecting them to science personally and emotionally.

3. Didactic games. The main goals of this method are:

- increase students' interest in science;
- activate cognitive activity simultaneously individually and collectively;
- develop observation, depth of thought, and the ability to notice unusual aspects in familiar phenomena;
- to stimulate and strengthen students' cognitive activity.

The main types of activity of a primary school student are play, education, and work. At the same time, play prepares the student not only for study, but also for work; in terms of its content and essence, it is both a form of education and work at the same time.

The effectiveness of didactic games is associated with the variety of their types: role-playing games, games with rules, correctional games, seminar games, etc. This variety allows each student to choose a form of game that suits his interests and the activity in which he can successfully participate. When the game is aimed at an educational goal, it becomes a didactic game.

Pedagogical practice shows that game-based lessons:

- significantly increases students' interest in science;
- helps to remember definitions, terms, and formulas easily and firmly;
- encourages students to think freely and increases their cognitive activity.

Researchers say that lessons using didactic games achieve the following results:

- learning material is learned more easily and more deeply;
- each student is actively involved in the lesson process;
- Individualized control is created for each task;
- the level of motivation for learning increases;
- The communication between teacher and student improves qualitatively.

4. The project method is an effective pedagogical technology that serves to develop students' cognitive activity, form socially significant qualities, achieve results based on practical activities, and cultivate the skills of working in collective cooperation.

Project types are classified as follows:

By purpose:

Research project (scientific) – a scientific-analytical approach to a problem;

Information project - collection, analysis and presentation of information;

Creative project – tasks performed in free and unusual forms;

A role-playing project is organized by assigning roles in a fairy tale, story, or historical context.

According to the content :

Mono-project – carried out within the framework of one discipline;

Interdisciplinary project – covers multiple subjects or is carried out as an extracurricular activity.

By scale :

Classroom, intra-school, local, regional, international projects.

By duration :

Mini-project – during one lesson;

Short-term project – 2-3 lessons or weekly;

Medium and long-term projects are carried out throughout the academic year.

In practice, primary school students usually participate in mini and short-term projects, mainly within the classroom. For example, in the 4th grade, a project on the topic of "Punctuation Marks" in the subject of the native language can be created. In this case, the project summarizes previous knowledge, the main goal is to find an answer to the question "Why are punctuation marks needed?" through research and presentation. The student:

- seeks information,
- expresses his/her opinion,
- defends the presentation.

At the end of the project, students ask each other questions and exchange ideas. Having students independently choose which punctuation mark to talk about increases their engagement and interest.

The development of cognitive activity using the project method requires the creation of the following conditions:

- creating a friendly and collaborative environment in the classroom;
- creating a "success situation" for every student;
- involving all students in team activities;
- review new or previously learned topics through unconventional assignments;
- taking into account the individual characteristics of students;

- encourage only positive attitudes and emotions;
- Maximum attention to thinking - this stimulates cognitive activity.

Therefore, the primary school teacher:

- It should take into account the interests of students and at the same time form their learning motivations;
- involve them in solving problem situations;
- should use didactic games, debates, and various methods.

Curiosity, wonder, amazement, and connection to real-life experiences encourage students to actively participate. Students' ability to defend their opinions, participate in debates, ask questions, and try to find multiple solutions to a problem all stimulate cognitive activity.

As a result of the study of the approaches studied, the pedagogical and didactic conditions necessary for the development of cognitive activity of primary school students, the classification of stages and levels of development of cognitive activity, and the requirements for the teacher to organize didactic activities, the following conclusions were reached:

Primary school age is an important stage in the development of cognitive activity in children. The leading developmental factor during this period is the guiding role of adults, especially the teacher. The teacher is the main person who manages and develops the cognitive activity of students.

Thus, developing students' cognitive activity in primary education is not just about imparting knowledge, but also an important pedagogical process aimed at shaping the student as an active, independent, and creatively thinking individual who seeks knowledge.

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